

The playlist pipeline

Reconstructing the historical music programming of the Indonesian programme of Radio Netherlands Wereldomroep

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One of the most important yet underresearched topics in radio history is programming. Potter (2022) argues that studying programming reveals how international broadcasting functioned as soft power and public diplomacy. Despite its relevance, radio historians have largely overlooked this topic, as the abundance and heterogeneity of source material (radio guides, logbooks, cue sheets) has proved a formidable hurdle. While some studies have sampled limited intervals (MacLennan 2005), we lack systematic methods to reconstruct programming strategies over longer periods. This paper addresses that gap by presenting a computational pipeline to reconstruct the historical playlists of the Indonesian programme of Radio Netherlands Wereldomroep (RNW), 1950–1966, and reporting findings on music and genre trends transmitted to Indonesian audiences.

Data

The RNW left an extensive set of broadcast logbooks (1950–1966), digitised by the KITLV in Leiden. The collection comprises cue sheets, daily reports (*dagrapport*), technical logs, news scripts, and music programme sheets. Of these, daily reports (Figure 1) and music programme sheets consistently contain extractable music references with record identifiers that enable linking to commercial releases.

Methods

The pipeline proceeds in four stages: (1) document parsing, converting PDF page images to structured Markdown using Infinity-Parser-7B (82.5 on olmOCR-Bench); (2) classification, identifying music-bearing pages via fuzzy regex detection of document-type headers; (3) metadata extraction, using Qwen2.5-VL 32B Instruct AWQ prompted with three few-shot examples per document type to extract label, catalog number, artists, and broadcast time per entry; (4) linking, matching extracted identifiers to the Discogs music database via a four-step rule-based fallback with label normalisation. The overall match rate is 56.7% (40,244 of 71,016 records), rising from 48% in 1950 to approximately 70% for 1965–66.

A key methodological consideration is that Indonesian repertoire matches at a lower rate (21.6%) than non-Indonesian records (58.8%). This differential does not affect the Indonesian share analysis presented below, because records are classified as Indonesian prior to matching, using label names, catalogue number patterns, and title-language detection. Discogs metadata underpins the genre and style analyses; inverse-probability weighting to correct for the fact that some record types match more often than others

changes genre shares by less than 1 percentage point, indicating the matched subset is representative. Full evaluation results will be presented at the conference.

Findings

The findings reveal two interconnected dynamics in RNW's music programming: the expansion of Western popular music genres and the simultaneous contraction of Indonesian repertoire.

Genre analysis shows that Rock & Roll's rise was one of expansion rather than displacement (Figure 2). Its share among style-tagged records crossed Swing's between 1959 and 1960 (11.5% vs. 11.7% in 1959; 20.8% vs. 11.2% in 1960). Bayesian regression on daily report pages shows Rock & Roll's absolute count growing by roughly 32% per year (rate ratio 1.32, 94% credible interval [1.27, 1.37]), while Swing remained essentially flat (RR 1.02, 94% CI [0.97, 1.05]). By 1965, Rock & Roll reached 29% share and Swing had declined to 5. This is not because Swing records disappeared, but because the expanding playlist diluted their share.

This growth was driven entirely by non-Indonesian material. Beneath the modestly growing total playlist (+78 records/yr, $p=0.001$), two opposing trends are visible: non-Indonesian records rise from 3,288 to 4,348 (+87/yr, $p<0.001$), while Indonesian records decline from 427 to 153 (-9/yr, $p=0.01$). Indonesian repertoire fell from 11.5% of all records in 1950 to 3–4% by 1965–66, and from 12.7% to approximately 3% when restricted to Indonesian-service broadcasts only. Bayesian Beta regression confirms a robust decline for all extract music records (-0.32%/yr, 94% CI [-0.49, -0.16]) and when restricted to daily reports only (-0.45%/yr, 94% CI [-0.64, -0.29]). The Indonesian-service subset is inconclusive (-0.17%/yr, 94% CI [-0.41, +0.07]), compatible with both a modest decline and no change (Figure 3).

Discussion

Together, these findings raise important questions about the cultural politics of post-colonial public diplomacy. RNW's Indonesian service was ostensibly designed to maintain ties with Indonesian audiences after independence, yet its music programming increasingly prioritised Western repertoire. Whether this shift reflected deliberate editorial policy, the growing availability of Western recordings, or the deteriorating state of Dutch-Indonesian relations and subsequent diplomatic rupture cannot be determined from programming data alone, but the pipeline provides the empirical foundation to pursue such questions systematically. The enriched dataset will be made publicly available, enabling further research into RNW's programming history and the role of music in international broadcasting more broadly.

Literature

Badenoch, Alexander, 'Radio Diffusion: Re-collecting International Broadcasting in the Archive of Radio Netherlands Worldwide', in: Golo Föllmer and Alexander Badenoch (eds.),

Transnationalizing Radio: New Approaches to an Old Medium Research (Transcript: Bielefeld 2018) 209-222.

MacLennan, Anne F. 'What Do the Radio Program Schedules Reveal?', in: Jeff Keshen and Sylvie Perrier (eds.), *Building New Bridges - Bâtir De Nouveaux Ponts* University of Ottawa Press: Ottawa 2005) 225-238.

Potter, Simon J., 'Programmes, Soft Power and Public Diplomacy', in S.J. Potter et al., *The Wireless World: Global Histories of International Broadcasting* (Oxford University Press: Oxford 2022) pp.167-187.

RADIO NEDERLAND WERELDOMROEP			RAPPORT VAN DE UITZENDING
DAG EN DATUM: Zaterdag 2 Januari 1964			STUDIOGEBOUW: II
VAN	TOT	AARD VAN HET PROGRAMMA	AANTEKENINGEN
12.55		Techniek: R. Vlsenderen Omroep/Pres.: G. Jochem Pauzeprogramma en stationcalls.	
13.00	Arda.	OPENING EN PROGRAMMA-OVERZICHT.	Band. (Vaste)
13.01	Jochem.	NIEUWSBULLETIN.	
13.10	Arda.	HET JAAR IN NEDERLAND! Inhoud teveel om op te noemen.	Band. 191.044
13.23	Pas.	MANA-SUKA, verzoekplatenprogramma.	Band. 191.049
2'19"		1. VALDERI VALDERA (A. Ridge/Fr. Möller) The Beverly Sisters + orch. W. Stott	U LP 3654 Phil. BBR 8052
2'12"		2. CAN'T BUY ME LOVE (Lennon/McCartney) The Beatles	H 23288 Parlophone R 5114
2'04"		3. AL DI LA (Donida/Mogol/Remy/Haag) Sandra Reemer met ork. Frans Kerkhof	H 21378 Phil. 318.776 PF
2'43"		4. PRETTY PAPER (W. Nelson) Roy Orbison	U 45-25225 London FLX 3139
2'19"		5. BRUIDSMARS (Mendelssohn-Bartholdy) Concertgeb. ork. olv. George Szell	H 8350 Phil. 400.058 AE
1'04"		6. SUMMER HOLIDAY (Welch/B Bennett) Cliff Richard + The Shadows	H 22297 Col. 45 OH 5001
2'28"		7. JUDY JUDY JUDY (Pomus/Shuman/Tillotson) Johnny Tillotson	U 45-22666 Cadence CC26228
2'22"		8. I NEED YOU (Baker Knight) Ricky Nelson	U 45-20852 IMP. AI 5901
2'03"		9. I SAW LINDA YESTERDAY (Lee/Reynolds) Dickey Lee	U 45-21049 Phil. 320158 BF
2'04"		10. I SAW LOVE WITH YOU TO YOU (C. Good)	U LP 10449 Phil. 318.776 PF
2'35"		10. THE END OF THE WORLD (Dee/Kent) Skeeter Davis	U 45-24319 RCA Victor EPA 4374
13.58	Jochem.	PROGRAMMA VAN MORGEN MET SLUITING EN SLOTTUNE.	
14.00	Jochem	EINDE EERSTE UITZENDING.	
14.15	tot 15.15	TWEDE UITZENDING CONFORM EERSTE (ook Mana-Suka)	

Figure 1: RNW logbook for 2 January 1965. The date mentioned in the logbook is an error. The record identifier is highlighted.

Figure 2: Rock & Roll/Beat and Swing/Big Band on daily report pages, 1950–1966. Left: share of style-tagged matched records, showing the crossover between 1959 and 1960. Right: absolute record counts with Bayesian 94% credible bands. Rock & Roll grows at a rate ratio of 1.32/yr (94% CI [1.27, 1.37]), while Swing is essentially flat (RR 1.02/yr, 94% CI [0.97, 1.05])

Figure 3. Indonesian repertoire share under three specifications, 1950–1966. Left: observed shares with Bayesian Beta regression 94% credible bands for all document types (red), daily reports only (blue), and Indonesian-service daily reports only (green). Right: posterior slope distributions showing the decline is robust across the first two specifications. Marginal effects: all records $-0.32\%/yr$ (94% CI $[-0.49, -0.16]$), daily reports $-0.45\%/yr$ (94% CI $[-0.64, -0.29]$), Indonesian-service $-0.17\%/yr$ (94% CI $[-0.41, +0.07]$).